

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3585552>urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:961708D7-D3D7-45FA-8C5D-49891BD06E49

The first record of *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Pamphiliidae) from Donbass and Ukrainian steppe

O. I. Gubin¹ & I. S. Levchenko²¹Ukrainian Entomological SocietyE-mail: helminolog@mail.ru²Russian Entomological SocietyE-mail: inna_levchenko@mail.ua

Gubin, O. I. & Levchenko, I. S. The first record of *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Pamphiliidae) from Donbass and Ukrainian steppe. — The web-spinning sawfly *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) is found in Donbass and Ukrainian steppe for the first time. Material was collected in May 2019. A distribution of the species is considered.

Key words: Hymenoptera, Pamphiliidae, *Caenolyda reticulata*, Donbass, Ukrainian steppe, first record.

Губін, О. І. і Левченко, І. С. Перша знахідка *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Pamphiliidae) в Донбасі і Степовій зоні України. — Павутинного пильщика *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) вперше знайдено в Донбасі і Степовій зоні України. Матеріал було зібрано у травні 2019. Розглянуто поширення виду.

Ключові слова: Hymenoptera, Pamphiliidae, *Caenolyda reticulata*, Донбас, Степова зона України, перша знахідка.

Introduction

The genus *Caenolyda* Konow, 1897 is represented by two species in the World and European fauna: widespread in Europe *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) and endemic of South Italy (Calabria) *C. binaghii* C. Pesarini & F. Pesarini, 1976 (van Achterberg & van Aartsen, 1986). In Ukraine *C. reticulata* is considered a rare and endangered species, which is known for several records from the Forest and from the north of the Forest-Steppe zones and included in the Red Data Book of Ukraine (Ermolenko & Kotenko, 2009). In May 2019, a specimen of *C. reticulata* was found on Scots pine *Pinus sylvestris* L. in the territory of Donetsk Botanical Gardens (Donetsk Region). This is the first record of this species from Donbass and Ukrainian steppe.

Material and methods

The specimen was collected by entomological sweep-net in May 2019. The photo was taken using a Zeiss AxioCam Erc 5s camera, mounted on Carl Zeiss Stemi 2000-C binocular microscope with Zen 2012 (blue edition) software package, and subsequently enhanced with Adobe Photoshop CS5 software package. The specimen (Fig. 1) is deposited in the collection of authors (Donetsk, Ukraine).

Results

Caenolyda reticulata (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 1)

Material examined: Ukraine: Donetsk Reg., Donetsk, Donetsk Botanical Gardens, 48.004114°N 37.525647°E, on *Pinus sylvestris* L., 16.05.2019, 1 ♀ (O. I. Gubin & I. S. Levchenko).

The range is disjunctive. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Hungary, Italy, Germany, Latvia, Luxemburg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, European Russia (Leningrad, Smolensk, Moscow, Vladimir, Kaluga, Tula, Ryazan and Ulyanovsk Regions), Ukraine (Lviv, Zhytomyr, Kyiv and Chernihiv Regions) (Nielsen, 1969; Tsharntke & Rühm, 1985; van Achterberg & van Aartsen, 1986; Ermolenko, 2001; Magis, 2005; Bakker & Bakker, 2007; Martínez de Murguía & Aguado, 2007; Ermolenko & Kotenko, 2009; Sheshurak, 2010; etc.). First record for the Donbass.

Monophagous. Larvae feed on needles of Scots pine *Pinus sylvestris* L., live by small groups in silk tubular nests. Monovoltine. Almost everywhere is very rare. Our record shows that artificial pine plantings contribute to the expansion of *C. reticulata* range and its conservation even in the urban areas of industrial regions.

Fig. 1. *Caenolyda reticulata*, habitus, female.

References

- Achterberg, C. van & Aartsen B. van. 1986. The European Pamphiliidae (Hymenoptera: Symphyta), with special reference to The Netherlands. *Zool. Verh. Leiden*, 234: 1–98.
- Bakker, W. & Bakker, F. 2007. De bladwesp *Caenolyda reticulata* nieuw voor de Nederlandse Fauna (Hymenoptera: Pamphiliidae). *Nederlandse Faunistische mededelingen*, 27: 19–21.
- Ermolenko, V. M. 2001. *Caenolyda reticulata* Linnaeus, 1767. In: *Red Data Book of the Russian Federation (animals)*. Moscow, AST, Astrel: 152. [In Russian].
- Ermolenko, V. M. & Kotenko, A. G. 2009. *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus, 1758). In: Akimov, I. A. (ed.), *Red Data Book of Ukraine. Animals*. Globalconsulting, Kyiv: 211. [In Ukrainian].
- Magis, N. 2005. Apports à la chorologie des Hyménoptères Symphytes de Belgique et du Grand-Duché de Luxembourg. XXIX. *Notes fauniques de Gembloux*, 56: 35–39.
- Martínez de Murguía, L. & Aguado, L. Ó. 2007. Primera cita para la Península Ibérica de *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Pamphiliidae). *Heteropterus Rev. Entomol.*, 7 (1): 123–125.
- Nielsen, B. O. 1969. Bladhvepsen *Cephalcia reticulata* (L.) (Hymenoptera: Pamphiliidae), ny for Danmark. *Flora og Fauna*, 75: 65–67.
- Sheshurak, P. N. 2010. To the necessity of preparation and publication of regional Red Data Books in Ukraine. *Species populations and communities in anthropogenic transformed landscapes: state and methods of its diagnostics. Materials of the XI International scientific and practical environmental conference. September 20–25, 2010, Belgorod*. CPI POLITERRA, Belgorod: 56–57. [In Russian].
- Tscharntke, T. & Rühm, W. 1985. Zur Verbreitung und Lebensweise der Genetzten Gespinstblattwespe *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus 1758) (Hymen., Pamphiliidae). *Anzeiger für Schädlingskunde, Pflanzenschutz, Umweltschutz*, 58: 35–36.